

Factors affect Canadian Women Purchase Intention in Green Cosmetics in the Frame of Moral Obligation, Green Trust, Self-Identity, Health, Social Value, and Satisfaction

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Abstract

Subsequently to the international trend of the obligation to preserve environment, the cosmetic's companies made their priorities to preserve the environment and supports the utilization of products that aims at maintaining the preservation of environment, and facing pollution. The answer of this trend was the green marketing, which focuses on the effective use of resources and aimed at giving the best value to customers and other parties without neglecting the long-term environmental and social needs. And this study goal is to investigate the relationship between green cosmetic purchase intention and the factors effect on green cosmetic purchase intention such as moral obligation, green trust, green self-identity, health consciousness, social value and satisfaction. The methodology used for this study is the quantitative method by distributing surveys on Canadian women. The founding of the study that there is a positive relation between purchase intention and social value, satisfaction and self identity, while we couldn't find a relation between green purchase intention and green trust, moral obligation, and health consciousness.

Keywords: Green Cosmetics, Green Trust, Green Purchase Intention, Satisfaction, Social Value, Self-Identity, Health, Moral Obligation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the sixties of the last century the world began to be very upset and worried about some environmental issues such as pollution and depletion of energy sources. (Vandermerwe & Oliff, 1990). Although business organizations consider environmental aspects as a key to increasing their competitiveness and maximizing their profitability by contributing to pollution control and environmental performance improvement, reducing costs and reducing accident rates, as well as increasing the efficiency and performance of employees, also respect for and preservation of the environment improves the reputation and image of the institution and increases its ability to acquire new markets and new consumers, the importance of this proposition is highlighted by the inclusion of the role played by institutions in the field of sustainable development, and their importance in the economic development, which is directly reflected at the social level. (Kassarjian, 1971).

The definition of cosmetics in the eyes of the Canadian governments is: A “cosmetic” is any substance used to improve, clean or change the complexion, hair, nail, teeth, or skin. (Canadian government, 2011). Cosmetics include beauty preparations (perfume, make-up, nail polish, skin cream) and grooming aids (soap, deodorant, shaving cream, and shampoo). In the year of 2021 the Canadian market value of cosmetics is anticipated to reach around 15.8 billion U.S dollars. In 2016 there were more than 3,100 beauty care, cosmetics and fragrance stores in Canada. In 2018 around twenty five percent of Canadians state that skin care products are the kind of cosmetics they buy and use frequently. Face care cosmetics products rank the first place in Canada with sales of cosmetics industry. In 2018 sales of skin care products reached approximately 929 million dollars. While products like hand and body moisturizers and sun care products came second and third in sales value of cosmetics products. Canadian family in 2016 spent on average 275 C.D on skincare, manicure, and make-up products. Canadians are more and more trying to find inexperienced merchandise and services, and plenty of them are even willing to pay additional for them, however they will be selective on that they choose based on the strength of environmental claims. (Emma, 2018).

Beauty and personal care continued to accomplish an impressive performance in Canada in 2018, with the present growth value outpacing the increase seen in 2017. Skin care has faced the most important growth, driven by consumers who are searching to preserve healthy skin, and an increasing willingness to spend on high-quality, premium products. In addition, the ongoing upbeat and sustainability trends are driving client interest in natural beauty and private care merchandise. (Carreras, 2004). Younger customers particularly are driving interest in sustainability and eco-friendliness, while customers across demographics are involved concerning potential health risks created by the employment of chemicals in beauty and private care merchandise, similarly as personal considerations like skin sensitivity and irritation. (Pieroni et al, 2004). In recent years, individual wellness has been associated with personal care and beauty products, when it comes to looking and feeling good Canadian consumers are searching for a comprehensive way. In other words, Canadian consumer when applying cosmetics on their skin it needs to be natural like the organic food they consume and as youth preserving as their exercise routine. (Carreras, 2004). The lifestyle movement of Canadian consumers is that they are converting in their daily use of skin care products to an ethical and organic skin product due to their greater quality naturel ingredients. Which procure ethical and organic skin care products to represents forty percent of the

Canadian skin market. Cosmetic companies are forced to make organic products due to the increased concerns on the effect of using cosmetics for long term. The market of organic cosmetics is expected to grow fast through the forecasted time. (Nema et al, 2011).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

When people hear the phrase green marketing, they think that it is only refers to advertising and promotion of products that have environmental properties. Couple of things consumer usually links green marketing with phrases like recyclable, phosphate free, environmentally friendly, and ozone friendly. (Skizinsky, 2000). In fact, these phrases are green marketing allegations, but green marketing has a wider concept, which can be enforced to industrial goods, consumer goods and also to services. (Durst & Ingram, 1989). Some model like, resorts all over the world that are starting to advertise themselves as ecotourist facilities, and facilities that specifies in testing nature or working in a way that decrease their environmental influence. (Skizinsky, 2000). Green marketing can be seen as a translation of the social and ethical responsibility of marketing, which came to light in response to the growing environmental challenges of the new era. (Wasik, John F,1996). Due to the changes in marketing practice after the entry of sustainability, there is obligation to consider sustainability to improve marketing strategy, which means that firm has to embrace sustainability in marketing mix and strategic marketing practices. (Slaper& Hall, 2011).

Sustainable marketing in marketing literature can be defined as the process of planning, implementing and pricing, promotion and distribution that come across the following three criteria: satisfying customer needs, achieving organizational objectives, relevance of the process to ecosystems. Achieving sustainable marketing requires two main approaches: Green marketing and social marketing. (Fuller, 1999). The concept on which sustainable marketing is based on is the responsibility of the social institution, that the orientation indicates the institutions succeed in working by interfering of the ethical principles with its actions, and to be sensitive to social and environmental problems and trends that give them an important competitive advantage. In order to make sustainable marketing orientation far from conventional vision. In terms of product policy all activities must be generated from ideas, and to make a new product within the framework of the vision of sustainability that focuses on satisfying all stakeholders and not influencing their long-term interests. (Whiting, 2008).

2.1 Concept of Purchase Intention

Marketing through different activities has been concerned with satisfying the needs and desires of the consumer and developing their products to achieve consumer satisfaction, so that the success of the organization is not limited to discovering the needs of the consumer, but to work doubly to determine the reasons for finding that need or other intentions and motives In order to capture the opinion polls (Tonita Perea, Dellaert & Ruyter, 2004). This requires careful study and careful analysis of the internal factors and motivations that drive the intention of others. Where goods can be defined as the need of consumers to satisfy them, whether basic or otherwise. Goods and services are one of the means used primarily to satisfy the desires of prospective consumers. (Kilbourne , 1995). The need for products is discovered through the interaction of external attention and internal motives that create the individual has a sense of need (Kotler, 1997).

Purchase intention can generally be defined as planning, planning, and making efforts to show off a specific product or service. (Chekiman et al., 2015). While the intention of purchasing a green product was identified as the individual's willingness and preference for green products rather than traditional products in the making of decision. (Lasuin & ching, 2014).

2.2 Factors Effecting Green Marketing

This study will only demonstrate some of the factors that affect green marketing:

Moral obligation

Haines defined moral obligation as the structure of a personal internal condition that depends on the range of responsibility to act morally when put in a situation with an ethical conflict that the person feels. (Haines et al., 2008). Koestner thinks that the person behaviour preferences are coming from assessment of what is moral and what is wrong or not moral within the area of green consumerism. (Koestner et al., 2001). In other words, when a consumer start living his life with the principle of eco friendly consumer it is because, it is the moral or right thing to do and the breaking of these principles is not moral and wrong. A consumer may feel guilty in an evoked shape of emotional sorrow and that may arouse expected negative emotion due to his awareness of not acting in the right way by purchasing product that harm the environment in a massive way. (Steenhaut& Kenhove, 2006). So, when a consumer buys an environmentally friendly product this act is reflecting a selfish motivation alleviate his own sorrow and make him feel positive emotions. (Steenhaut& Kenhove, 2006). Moral obligation manners have been found to importantly anticipate behaviours and intentions including moral dimensions, like in the situation of purchasing green products. (Sparks & Shepherd 2002, Shaw & Shiu 2003, Pelozo et al., 2013).

Green trust

Researchers proposed that in business settings building a trust is a substantial element. (Rotter, 1971). One of the essential deterrents of a long term consumer behaviour is the consumer trust. Hart and Sunders explained trust as the range of faith that the other team would show good act as anticipated. (Hart& Sunders, 1997). Trust can be defined as an anticipation kept by one side that the statement, word or promise of the other side can be depend on. (Schurr and Ozanne, 1985). This concludes the idea that consumer purchase intention is influenced by consumer trust. (Hair, 2006). The level of purchase intention would be higher if the customer had an old trusted relationship with the seller. (Harris and Goode, 2010). That's mean that customer trust comes before of the procedure of customer purchase intention. (Harris and Goode, 2010). Chen and Chang have defined the Green Trust as the willingness of a consumer to rely on a service or a product of a specific company based of his believes that this company has environmental credibility and ability. (Chen &Chang, 2013). Nowadays customers are hesitating in trusting some firms due to their inflating environmental performance of their products. (Van der Heijden et al., 2003). From this point of view, we conclude that in the current environmental period green trust would affect purchase intention behavior. (Chen, 2010). Old research found that the relationship between green trust and purchase intention was a positive relation. (Van der Heijden et al., 2003).

Green self-identity

Self identity usually understood as the way the individual distinguish himself. (Grubb and Grathwohl, 1967). And person self identity is influenced by two factors, personal

motivations factors that's come from self enhancement, self understanding and self esteem , and the other factor is the social interaction factor in the shape of expectations and demands of others and several roles that we do. (Tajfel & Turner, 1986, Ellemers, Spears, & Doosje, 2002, Stryker & Burke, 2000). In other study done by O'Neil and Whitmarsh, they identified two scales generic and behaviour specific where self identity can work in the context of supportive environmental behaviours. (O'Neil & Whitmarsh, 2010). The generic scales it describes the way the person see himself depend on his mental identifications with the normal green consumer. (Manetti et al., 2004). While the behaviour specific scale of green self identity describes the way, the consumer see himself depend on possible commitment in particular eco friendly attitudes like buying environmentally friendly product. (Shepred & Sparks, 1992). In order to satisfy consumers' self verification needs and increase individual satisfaction environmental friendly product might be a relevant way. (Stets & Burke, 2000). A lot of researchers have point out that there is a relation between self identity and purchase intention behaviour they are connected in relation to pro environmental actions. (Sankar & Bhattacharya, 2003). In a study that was done by Mannetti, he concludes that individuals how view themselves as a recycler have more probability to do recycling actions than those who do not. (Mannetti, 2004).

Health Consiousness

To reach a healthier lifestyle there are many manners that participate in it. (Schurr and Ozanne, 1985). It was confirmed from the psychological aspects a lower morbidity rate of disease within a locality is linked to living in a greener space of residential areas. (Ahmad, S.N.B. and N. Juhdi, 2008). Green purchase intention of Malaysian consumer is influenced by health concussions and perceived value. (Salleh, Ali, Harun, Jalil and Shaharudin, 2010). This result comes from the fact that consumers convinced about the beneficial of environmentally friendly product for a healthier life and help protect the environment. (Maas, Verheij, Vries, Spreeuwenberg, Schellevis and Groenewegen, 2009).

Social value

Sweeney and Soutar defined social value as the understanding of social self concept obtained from utilizing social trading sites. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). During the increasing of status and self esteem social value is achieved. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). When a consumer evaluates a product or a service, will not only evaluate it by pleasant and efficient values such as practical and environmental behaviour, but as well by social value. (Rintamaki et al., 2006). Researchers found that with a high level of consumer social value an increase in consumer satisfaction in relation to social business sites and stronger their purchase intention behaviour in social business context purchase intention. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). Studies have concluded that there is a strong and important relation between social value and purchase intention behaviour. (Rintamaki et al., 2006). Lin and Hsu from their study they found that there is an important and significant relation between social value and the intention of buying mobile applications. (Lin & Hsu, 2015). In other words, companies should understand social value like earning social consent, sensing that they fit and making a good impact on others, could make consumers to improve purchase intention. (Kim et al., 2013).

Consumer satisfaction

Oliver defined satisfaction as the assessment of business by consumers established on their anticipations and needs. (Oliver, 1980). Pointing out to consumer's positive

emotional state gained from utilizing the product or service. (Oliver, 1980). Satisfaction is a reflection of consumers' individual assessment coming from the comparison between their utilizing experience and their previous expectations about the product or service. (Lin & Hsu, 2015). Studies found that there is an important and critical role between satisfaction and its effect on consumer purchase intentions. (Zeithaml et al., 1996). A stronger purchase intention of a product or a service comes from an elevated level of satisfaction. (Oliver, 1980). A study done by Lin and Hsu showed that the purchase intention behaviour of mobile application was remarkably influenced by consumers' satisfaction. (Lin & Hsu, 2015). Another study done on the purchase intention of mobile added value services and they found a significantly important relation with the customers' satisfaction. (Kuo et al., 2009).

3. RESEARCH MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Model and Hypothesis

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between green cosmetic purchase intention and the factors effect on green cosmetic purchase intention such as moral obligation, green trust, green self-identity, health consciousness, social value and satisfaction. This research is a quantitative descriptive research aims to understand the relationship between one dependent variable and various independent variables.

Figure 1: The conceptual model of the study

The hypotheses emerging from the literature and the model of the study are presented at below.

- H₁: Green trust has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.
- H₂: Moral Obligation has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.
- H₃: Satisfaction has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.
- H₄: Health Consciousness has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.
- H₅: Self Identity has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.
- H₆: Social Value has a positive effect on green cosmetic purchase intention.

3.2 Questionnaire Design

Scales forming the questionnaire were gathered and were selected from valid and reliable scales by the literature review. Participants were completed 198 questioned survey with a five-point Likert scale (1= Strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= Neither agree nor disagree, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly agree) in order to evaluate their opinion related to “Green Trust”, “Moral Obligation”, “Satisfaction”, “Health Consciousness”, “Self Identity”, “Social Value” scales are examined in details at below in Table 1.

Table 1.1: Scales- Measurement items

Construct	Measurement	Reference
Green Trust	I feel that green cosmetics brand’s reputation is generally reliable.	Chen & Chang, 2012. Enhance Green Purchase Intentions: The Roles of Green Perceived Value, Green Perceived Risk, and Green Trust.
	I feel that green cosmetics brand’s performance is generally dependable.	
	I feel that green cosmetics brand’s claims are generally trustworthy.	
	Green cosmetics brand’s concern meets my expectation	
	Green cosmetics brand keeps promises and commitments for environmental protection	
Moral Obligation	I would feel guilty if I bought cosmetic products that damage the environment	Camilla Barbarossa & Patrick De Pelsmacker, 2014. Positive and Negative Antecedents of Purchasing Eco-friendly Products: A Comparison Between Green and Non-green Consumers
	Buying cosmetic products that damage the environment would be morally wrong for me	
	Buying cosmetic products that affect the environment would go against my principles	
4		
Satisfaction	I am satisfied with my decision on using this green cosmetic product.	Chunmei Gan, Weijun Wang, 2017. The influence of perceived value on purchase intention in social commerce context.
	I think that I did the right thing when I purchased this green cosmetic.	
	My choice to use this green cosmetic is a wise one.	
	My experience with using this green cosmetic is satisfactory.	
Health Consciousness	I believe the outcome of green cosmetics and beauty care products is better than synthetic cosmetics and beauty care products	Sharmila, Thanika, Yogini, 2015. Gender-based differences in understanding the purchasing patterns of eco-friendly cosmetics and beauty care products in Mauritius: A study of female customers
	I choose green cosmetics because of the natural ingredients.	
	Green cosmetics are suitable for my allergy problems.	
	Green cosmetics are safe for health	
Green Self Identity	I think of myself as someone who is concerned about environmental issues	Camilla Barbarossa & Patrick De Pelsmacker ,2014. Positive and Negative Antecedents of Purchasing
	I think of myself as a ‘green’ consumer	

Buying green cosmetic products would make me feel like a green consumer

Eco-friendly Products: A Comparison Between Green and Non-green Consumers.

I would feel totally satisfied with myself if I bought green cosmetic products

	Using this green cosmetic would help me to feel acceptable.	
	Using this green cosmetic would help me to feel acceptable.	Chunmei Gan, Weijun Wang, 2017
Social Value	Using this green cosmetic would improve the way I am perceived.	The influence of perceived value on purchase intention in social commerce context.
	Using this green cosmetic would give its owner social approval.	
Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention	I am willing to pay more for green cosmetics products.	Azmawani, Ebrahim, Suhaimi, 2015.
	I am willing to shop around to buy green cosmetics.	Consumers and Halal cosmetic products: knowledge, religiosity, attitude and intention.
	I intent to purchase green cosmetics products in the future.	

3.3 Sampling and Data Collection

Data were assembled from 198 cosmetic female purchasers in Canada. Convenient sampling is implemented to data and accumulated all through May and June 2019. A total of 213 questionnaires had been collected via Google online survey (The required data for the current study was collected through a questionnaire- see appendix 1). Consequently, a complete of 198 responses have been used for further analyses. First sixty questionnaires were pre-tested in order to correct the mistakes of the draft questionnaire and control the reliability of the related scales. To calculate the size of sample formula proposed by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) was used (2007) in the study. $N > 50 + 8m$ is the formule used. Where N refers sample size, m refers number of independent variables. Based on this formula required sample size for current research is defined as 98 (as the number of independent variables equals to six). Consequently, sample size is defined as 198 which exceed the minimum threshold.

4 ANALYSIS

IBM SPSS 24.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) program was used for the analyses of the primary data collected. With demographic data, descriptive statistical analysis was conducted. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the research model respectively.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

All the respondents are female. 41,8 % of the respondents (82 people) are single and 59,5 % of them are married (115 people). 19,2 % (38 people) were graduated from high school or less and 17,7% (35 people) has graduated from a certificate programme. It is also observed that almost the majority of the sample (27,3 % of the participants, 54 people) have graduated from bachelor degree. Post-graduation degree was represented by the percentage of 22,3% with 64 people. There are seven foreign degreed people in the percentage of 3,5. Annual income distribution of the sample is gathered around in the range of 25.000 CAD-74.000 CAD with 144 people, 72,7%. 57,6 % of the respondents

(114 people) are working for public sector, while 41,4 % (82 people) are working for private sector. There are also two students in the respondents' profile.

A summary of demographic characteristics of respondents is provided in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Demographics

	Frequency	Percent (%)		Frequency	Percent (%)
Marital Status			Income (Annual)		
Single	82	41,8	Less than 9999 CAD	3	1,5
Married	115	59,5	10.000 CAD-24.999 CAD	31	15,7
Education			25.000 CAD- 49.000 CAD	77	38,9
High School or less	38	19,2	50.000 CAD-74.999 CAD	67	33,8
Certificate	35	17,7	75.000 CAD- 99.999 CAD	20	10,1
Bachelor Degree	54	27,3	Mora than 100.000 CAD	0	0
Master's Degree	25	12,6	Occupation		
Professional Degree	21	10,6	Public sector employee	114	57,6
PhD degree	18	9,1	Private sector employee	82	41,4
Foreign degree	7	3,5	Student	2	1
TOTAL	251	100	TOTAL	198	100

4.2 Descriptive Statistics and Normal Distribution

Normality assessment is one of the prerequisites of parametric analysis. In order to conduct multiple regression analyses it is crucial to ensure that the given data is multivariate normal. All metric variables were tested with Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality test and it had been confirmed that all of them distributed normally ($p > 0,005$). The values of mean, variance and standard deviation of each item is presented in the Table 4.2 as a descriptive statistic.

4.3 Reliability Analysis

Reliability is related to the degree to which test results are free of measurement error. Additionally, the reliability examines how consistent the measured item is among respondents and steadiness of the characteristics across time period (Smith and Albaum, 2005). Table 4.3 depicts the reliability assessment of each construct. The reliability has been established as Cronbach alpha value is above 0.7 for each construct. All the variables in the research got the higher Cronbach alfa values than 0,70 and found quite reliable.

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic
moral1	198	1.00	5.00	19.848	150.962
moral2	198	1.00	5.00	39.545	.88010
moral3	198	1.00	5.00	40.000	.90683
trust1	198	1.00	5.00	40.253	.94217
trust2	198	1.00	5.00	40.808	.91991
trust3	198	1.00	5.00	408.081	.880433
trust4	198	1.00	5.00	40.354	.97364
trust5	198	1.00	5.00	40.505	.95454
identity1	198	1.00	5.00	40.859	.85953
identity2	198	1.00	5.00	41.263	.85450
identity3	198	1.00	5.00	40.101	.99230
identity4	198	1.00	5.00	40.859	.88856
health1	198	1.00	5.00	40.657	.90162
health2	198	1.00	5.00	40.303	.92845
health3	198	2.00	5.00	41.212	.82194
health4	198	1.00	5.00	40.707	.92074
social1	198	1.00	5.00	42.020	.84876
social2	198	1.00	5.00	40.354	.95256
social3	198	1.00	5.00	39.949	.93166
social4	198	1.00	5.00	40.101	100.248
sat1	198	1.00	5.00	39.697	.98160
sat2	198	1.00	5.00	41.313	.93599
sat3	198	1.00	5.00	41.212	.89865
sat4	198	1.00	5.00	41.667	.91657
int1	198	1.00	5.00	41.515	.93291
int2	198	1.00	5.00	40.253	.99459
int3	198	1.00	5.00	40.556	101.359
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Table 4.3: Reliability Analysis Scores of Scales

Construct	Measurement items	Cronbach Alfa Value
Green Trust	I feel that green cosmetics brand's reputation is generally reliable.	0,942
	I feel that green cosmetics brand's performance is generally dependable.	
	I feel that green cosmetics brand's claims are generally trustworthy.	
	Green cosmetics brand's concern meets my expectation	
	Green cosmetics brand keeps promises and commitments for environmental protection	
Moral Obligation	I would feel guilty if I bought cosmetic products that damage the environment	0,886
	Buying cosmetic products that damage the environment would be morally wrong for me	
	Buying cosmetic products that affect the environment would go against my principles	
Satisfaction	I am satisfied with my decision on using this green cosmetic product.	0,936
	I think that I did the right thing when I purchased this green cosmetic.	
	My choice to use this green cosmetic is a wise one.	
Health Consciousness	My experience with using this green cosmetic is satisfactory.	0,895
	I believe the outcome of green cosmetics and beauty care products is better than synthetic cosmetics and beauty care products	
	I choose green cosmetics because of the natural ingredients.	
	Green cosmetics are suitable for my allergy problems.	

Green Self Identity	Green cosmetics are safe for health	0,909
	I think of myself as someone who is concerned about environmental issues	
Social Value	I think of myself as a 'green' consumer	0,909
	Buying green cosmetic products would make me feel like a green consumer	
	I would feel totally satisfied with myself if I bought green cosmetic products	
Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention	Using this green cosmetic would help me to feel acceptable.	0,936
	Using this green cosmetic would help me to feel acceptable.	
	Using this green cosmetic would improve the way I am perceived.	
Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention	Using this green cosmetic would give its owner social approval.	0,936
	I am willing to pay more for green cosmetics products.	
	I am willing to shop around to buy green cosmetics.	
	I intent to purchase green cosmetics products in the future.	

4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple Regression analysis is defined as a reliable method followed in statistics for identifying the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. By regression analysis, which variables have an impact on the research topic of interest and also the degree of that impact can be observed. In standard multiple regression, all the independent variables are evaluated in terms of its predictive power, over and above that offered by all the other independent variables and this approach is explain how much variance a set of variables explain dependent variable. On the other hand, there are some assumptions of multiple regression analysis such as sample size, multicollinearity, outliers, normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and interdependence of residuals in order to implement related analysis to the data (Pallant, 2010). Preliminary analysis was conducted to ensure no violation of the assumptions of sample size, multicollinearity, outliers and normality, linearity, homoscedasticity in order to conduct regression analysis to data.

According to the Anova table that was performed in Multiple regression analysis, the whole model of Green Cosmetic Purchase Intention is statically significant ($t= 1,918$, $p=0.000$). In addition, according to the Coefficient table, social identity ($t=2,263$, $p=0.025$, $p<0,05$), social value ($t= 3,108$, $p=0.002$) and satisfaction ($t=7,072$, $p=0.000$) have an effect on green cosmetic purchase intention in the 95% confidence interval, while green trust ($t= -0,061$, $p=0.952$, $p>0,05$), health consciousness ($t= 0,369$, $p=0.712$, $p>0,05$) and moral obligation ($t= 0,627$, $p=0.531$, $p>0,05$) have no effect on green purchase intention statistically ($p>0,05$). Independent variables of satisfaction, social value social identity and explain the dependent variable green cosmetic purchase intention by 83% ($R=0,913$; $R^2 =0,833$, $F=158,840$, $p=0,000$). In this relationship, the highest explanatory rate is owned by satisfaction ($\beta=0,571$), respectively social value ($\beta=0,258$), social identity ($\beta=0,175$). In addition to that, the tolerance value of all variables is above 0.10 and the VIF value is less than 10 means that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables (Pallant, 2010, p:156).

Table 4.4: The Results of Regression Analysis

	β	t value	p	F value	p	R	R2	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0,962	1,918	1,918	158,840	,000 ^b	,913 ^a	0,833		
Green trust	-.028	-0.061	.952					.128	7.833
Identity	.175	2.263	.025					.153	6.541
Health Consciousness	.030	0.369	.712					.148	6.745
Social Value	.258	3.108	.002					.163	6.128
Satisfaction	.571	7.072	.000					.143	6.998
Moral Obligation	.046	.627	.531					.193	5.189

Dependent Variable: Green Cosmetic Purchase Intention

According to the multiple regression analysis results, H₁, H₃, H₄ were accepted ($p < 0,005$), while H₂ is rejected ($p > 0,005$). Summary table of hypothesis tests are shown at below (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5: Summary Table of Hypothesis Tests

Hypotheses	Path	Accepted/R ejected
H ₁	Green Trust → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Rejected
H ₂	Moral Obligation → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Rejected
H ₃	Satisfaction. → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Accepted
H ₄	Health Consciousness → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Rejected
H ₅	Self- Identity → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Accepted
H ₆	Social Value → Green Cos. Purch. Int	Accepted

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We can recognize in this decade that the green market is still considered to be a niche, although there has been extended studies about the socially responsible consumer or the green consumer. It is recognized that purchase intentions are not linear and they combine extra emotional interference to the process of purchase of ethical brands or products, not only the rational decision making concerning functional product benefits like price or quality. For this reason, it is important to understand what is really important for the consumers thus managers and marketers can present relevant products that target genuine consumption

needs and that will participate in turning the niche into a wider market in a shortest amount of time. This study proposes and tests a model of green cosmetics purchasing intention that is influenced by consumer moral obligation to environment, consumer green trusting, consumer green self-identity, consumer health and consumer satisfaction. The results of this study have shown that there is a positive relation between consumer satisfaction and purchase intention. This result is compatible with previous findings. (Chunmei Gan & Weijun Wang, 2017, Zhang et al., 2015; Kuo et al., 2009). The using of commerce sites by a satisfied consumer can make him realize that it is a clever decision and is satisfactory with the sites, this will lead to the possibility of him being more likely to purchase from the sites and recommend it to other consumers. (Zeithaml et al., 1996; Cronin et al., 2000). Consumer satisfaction have shown a great effect among all of the other factors which indicates that companies should give a huge attention to the value of the green product. Consumers emphasis strongly on the end value of the product so that they will repurchase it again. This satisfaction would result to an increase in market shares, brand loyalty, and sales. (Shweta Singh, Deepak Singh and Thakur, 2014).

The study also found that there is a positive relation between consumer self-identity and green cosmetic purchase intention. Eisler et al. proposed that personal values are important stimulus of a consumer's involvement. (Eisler et al., 2003). A study done by Tracie et al. they found also that there is a positive relationship between consumers' green self-identity and efficient involvements toward eco-friendly apparel. In other words, a consumer who is environmentally conscious will more probably value the green attributes of ecofriendly apparel and will also develop efficient attachments with the product. (Tracie et al. 2017). There was also a significant relation between social value and consumer green cosmetics purchase intention. Chunmei Gan & Weijun Wang also found that there is a significant relation between social value and satisfaction and purchase intention. (Chunmei Gan & Weijun Wang, 2017). This result is likewise compatible with the finding of other studies. (Hsu and Lin, 2016; Hu et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2013; Li et al., 2012; Lin and Lu, 2015). Unexpectedly the findings showed that there isn't a relation between women purchase intention of green cosmetics and green trust, moral obligation and health consciousness. While in other studies moral obligation have been found significantly important for consumer green purchase intention. (Sparks and Shepherd 2002, Shaw and Shiu 2003, Peloza et al. 2013). Camilla Barbarossa & Patrick De Pelsmacker argued that there is a positive relation between consumer moral obligation and his purchase intention. (Camilla Barbarossa & Patrick De Pelsmacker, 2014). Chen & Chang they found a significant relationship between green trust and green purchase intention. (Chen & Chang, 2012). While Chen & Chang have found that there is a positive relationship between consumer health and eco-friendly purchase intention. (Chen & Chang, 2013). Likewise, Salleh, Ali, Harun, Jalil and Shaharudin they found a significant relation between consumer health consciousness and their purchase intention of green product. (Salleh, Ali, Harun, Jalil and Shaharudin, 2010).

5 LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

We justify our results to the limitation of the study. The first limitation is that it was distributed between a small sample size which is (N=198) and this is because of the time limit to complete the study. The other limitation is that this study was not distributed between a diverse culture sample, because all the participants where coming from the same culture.

This study offers awareness for marketers and cooperates into how to attract and keep consumers in the market of green cosmetics. The results highlight the significant effect of consumer satisfaction on purchase intention of green cosmetics, implying that cooperates

should take actions to improve consumer satisfaction by strengthening consumers' benefits and diminishing their of environmental risks, it will stimulates consumers' purchase intention. The study also reveals the importance of social value on consumer purchase intention. From that we can say that cooperates should put more attention to their product social value, because when a consumer wants to purchase a product, they will look about social value of this product, how it is positively influencing the environment and the important of word of mouth. The study also found that there is a positive relation between green cosmetics purchase intention and customer self-identity. This mean that marketers should give more attention to consumers identity, consumer is motivated to act consistently with his identity, that become the point of his goal striving and push to corrective behavior. Also, this study gives a path to researchers to do more researches on how individual factors like culture and self-image would have a positive relation with purchase intention. Additionally, studying the non-significant dimension on a bigger and more divers sample.

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